
The article provides a systematic analysis of classical and modern approaches to the formation of the concepts of “entrepreneurship”, “investment development” and “innovative development”. Original definitions are proposed. A conceptual model of an entrepreneurship support mechanism has been developed that integrates the institutional and legal framework, financial and investment instruments, digital platforms, and cluster development. The model is supplemented with a monitoring framework based on the calculation of the Investment Attractiveness Index and the Innovation Activity Index, which provides feedback and tailors support measures. The scientific novelty lies in the synthesis of theoretical propositions on entrepreneurship, investment, and innovation into a unified management framework, as well as the proposal of specific measures of management effectiveness. The practical significance lies in the fact that the model can be used by government agencies and regional administrations to develop entrepreneurship support programs aimed at stimulating investment and innovation.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, investment development, innovative development, theoretical aspects, management mechanism, Russia, institutional environment, digital transformation, cluster development, investment attractiveness index, innovation activity index.

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.

[1-13].

«

»

«

»,

.....

(,),
-
-37 ,
45 % (44 %) 35 (41,5 %),

— 2024 « »

2024 10,6 () 200
} « » ;

2024 () 53
2,2 (61 %), (53 %),
(50 %),

1. 2024 ,

2. , .. ,

« » ,
3. , -
« »

4. 2025-2026 —
(2024 . — 709),

1.

1

« — »

) — ;

) - ;

— (), ().

) - —

— ; —

« — »

—

« »

) ;

) (, ,);

) (, ,);

« — « »

) « » (, ,);

) « » (, ,);

) « » (, ,);

() ; - () ; - () ;

() ; - () ; - () ;

) ;

.I.

()

)
)

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

- 1.

- 2.

- 3.

- 4.

- 1.

- 2.

- 3.

- 4.

1. . . . : , / , 2024. — 210 . — EDN LZPGUB.
2. . . . // — 2023. — 14, 4. — 50-56. — DOI 10.18287/2542-0461-2023-14-4-50-56. — EDN CRNPRO.
3. . . . « » / . . . // . — 2015. — 6(6). — 26-31. — EDN VVFMNR.
4. . . . // 6: . — 2010. — 5. — 3-14. — EDN NCEHPD.
5. . . . // . — 2022. — 2(136). — 53-58. — DOI 10.26726/1812-7096-2022-2-53-58. — EDN ZCJPRU.
6. . . . // . — 2017. — 1(25). — 51-53. — EDN XICECZ.
7. . . . // « - » . — 2016. — 2. — 96-100. — EDN WAZPCF.
8. . . . // : , . — 2024. — 17, 1. — 159-177. — DOI 10.15838/esc.2024.1.91.9. — EDN LDTNRD.
9. . . . () / // - . — 2012. — 1. — 109-116. — EDN OXQGBT.
10. . . . // : « », 2014. — 8-27. — EDN LXONXF.
11. : // ; - : , 2024. — 458 .
12. . . . // « » / . — 2019. — 5(71), 4. — 54-63. — EDN EXEMDM.
13. . . . « » / . . . // : . — 2012. — 3. — 83-87. — EDN PIBPOL.
14. . — URL: www.rosstat.gov.ru/ (: 17.11.2025).
15. // . — URL: www.rosstat.gov.ru/investment_nonfinancial (: 17.11.2025).
16. 2024 7,4% // . — URL: www.interfax.ru/business/1012581 (: 17.11.2025).
17. : 2024 // (deloros.ru). — URL: deloros.ru/press-centr/novosti/glavnye-novosti/obshchestvennyy-sovet-minekonomrazvitiya-podvel-itogi-2024-goda-i-oboznachil-prioritetnye-zadachi-/?ysclid=mk8mh6sl4x167884141 (: 17.11.2025).

. — URL: cbr.ru/Collection/Collection/File/55991/inf_material_msp_2024.pdf (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

19. «». — URL: sk.ru/?q=N4IgzIBcoC4IYHMD OB9GBPADgUyiA9gE4gA 0IS2chAxBZ4BqASiAL5IJ4Am2YcArgBsYpEJigBGVKA (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

SPISOK LITERATURY

1. Ivanov, S. L. Razvitiye innovacionnogo predprinimatel'stva v rossijskih regionah: specifika, problemy, osnovnye napravleniya : dissertaciya na soiskanie uchenoj stepeni kandidata ekonomicheskikh nauk / Ivanov Semen Leonidovich, 2024. — 210 s. — EDN LZPGUB.

2. Zhugalev, I. I. Investicii v innovacionnoe razvitiye rossijskogo predprinimatel'stva i ego gosudarstvennaya podderzhka / I. I. Zhugalev // Vestnik Samarskogo universiteta. Ekonomika i upravlenie. — 2023. — T. 14, № 4. — S. 50-56. — DOI 10.18287/2542-0461-2023-14-4-50-56. — EDN CRNPRO.

3. Avdeeva, E. G. Teoriticheskie aspekty opredeleniya ponyatiya «predprinimatel'stvo» / E. G. Avdeeva // Teoriya i praktika sovremennoj nauki. — 2015. — № 6(6). — S. 26-31. — EDN VVFMNR.

4. Nikolaev, A. B. Teoreticheskie aspekty innovacionnogo razvitiya / A. B. Nikolaev, M. N. Os'mova // Vestnik Moskovskogo universiteta. Seriya 6: Ekonomika. — 2010. — № 5. — S. 3-14. — EDN NCEHPD.

5. Arslanov, Sh. D. Investicionnoe razvitiye regiona: problemy i perspektivy / Sh. D. Arslanov // Regional'nye problemy preobrazovaniya ekonomiki. — 2022. — № 2(136). — S. 53-58. — DOI 10.26726/1812-7096-2022-2-53-58. — EDN ZCJPRU.

6. Cherkasova, M. I. Investicionnoe obespechenie razvitiya predprinimatel'skoj deyatel'nosti v regione / M. I. Cherkasova // Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya. — 2017. — № 1(25). — S. 51-53. — EDN XICECZ.

7. Taranchuk, E. A. Teoreticheskie i prakticheskie aspekty innovacionnogo razvitiya v Rossijskoj Federacii / E. A. Taranchuk, A. N. Grigoryan // Nauchno-analiticheskij zhurnal «Vestnik Sankt-Peterburgskogo universiteta Gosudarstvennoj protivopozharnoj sluzhby MCHS Rossii». — 2016. — № 2. — S. 96-100. — EDN WAZPCF.

8. Ivanov, S. L. Problemy razvitiya innovacionnogo predprinimatel'stva v regione i puti ih resheniya / S. L. Ivanov, S. V. Terebova // Ekonomicheskie i social'nye peremeny: fakty, tendencii, prognoz. — 2024. — T. 17, № 1. — S. 159-177. — DOI 10.15838/esc.2024.1.91.9. — EDN LDTNRD.

9. Blagov, Yu. E. R. Edvard Frimen i koncepciya zainteresovannykh storon (predislovie k razdelu) / Yu. E. Blagov // Vestnik Sankt-Peterburgskogo universiteta. Menedzhment. — 2012. — № 1. — S. 109-116. — EDN OXQQBT.

10. Miroshnichenko, I. V. Setevoy podhod v politicheskikh issledovaniyah / I. V. Miroshnichenko // Seti v publichnoj politike : Politicheskaya nauka : Ezhegodnik / Rossijskaya asociaciya politicheskoy nauki. — Moskva : Izdatel'stvo «Politicheskaya enciklopediya», 2014. — S. 8-27. — EDN LXONXF.

11. Opyt o prirode kommercii: obshchie voprosy / Richard Kantil'on ; obshchaya redakciya toma, perevod s francuzskogo i anglijskogo O. I. Anan'ina. — Moskva : Izd-vo Instituta Gajdara ; Sankt-Peterburg : Centr ekonomicheskogo kul'tury, 2024. — 458 s.

12. Majdanevich, Yu. P. Evolyuciya i sushchnostnye karakteristiki ponyatiya «predprinimatel'stvo» / Yu. P. Majdanevich, K. A. Chuprynina, N. N. Grigor' // Uchenye zapiski Krymskogo federal'nogo universiteta imeni V.I. Vernadskogo. Ekonomika i upravlenie. — 2019. — T. 5(71), № 4. — S. 54-63. — EDN EXEMDM.

13. Golikova, O. G. Genezis ponyatiya «predprinimatel'stvo» / O. G. Golikova // Sovremennaya vysshaya shkola: innovacionnyj aspekt. — 2012. — № 3. — S. 83-87. — EDN PIBPOL.

14. Rosstat. — URL: www.rosstat.gov.ru/ (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

15. Investicii v nefinansovye aktivy // Rosstat. — URL: www.rosstat.gov.ru/investment_nonfinancial (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

16. Investicii v osnovnoj kapital v Rossii v 2024 godu vyrosli na 7,4% // Interfaks. — URL: www.interfax.ru/business/1012581 (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

17. DR: Obshchestvennyj sovet Minekonomrazvitiya podvel itogi 2024 goda i oboznachil prioritetye zadachi / Delovaya Rossiya (deloros.ru). — URL: deloros.ru/press-centr/novosti/glavnye-novosti/obshchestvennyj-sovet-minekonomrazvitiya-podvel-itogi-2024-goda-i-oboznachil-prioritetye-zadachi-/?ysclid=mk8mh6sl4x167884141 (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

18. Po itogam 2024 goda. Analiticheskij obzor rynka kreditovaniya sub'ektov malogo i srednego predprinimatel'stva. Informacionno-analiticheskij material. — Moskva. 2025. — URL: cbr.ru/Collection/Collection/File/55991/inf_material_msp_2024.pdf (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

19. Innovacionnyj centr «Skolkovo». — URL: sk.ru/?q=N4IgzIBcoC4IYHMD OB9GBPADgUyiA9gE4gA 0IS2chAxBZ4BqASiAL5IJ4Am2YcArgBsYpEJigBGVKA (data obrashcheniya: 17.11.2025).

24 2025

2 2025